

Phatak: A Cultural Festival of Injigan

Ali Akber Qazi

Ph.D. Scholar, Area Study Centre for Central Asia, University of Peshawar.
akber.kazy@gmail.com

Dr. Mohammad Ali
Dinakhel

Research supervisor to the author and faculty member at the Area Study
Centre for Central Asia, University of Peshawar. aliasc@uop.edu.pk

Abstract: *This article explores a beautiful cultural festival 'Phatak', which is celebrated in Injigan (Lotkuh), Chitral. It examines its origins, ritualistic structure, religious features and socio-cultural significance. Indigenous oral traditions associate the festival with the 11th century Ismaili philosopher and thinker Hakeem Nasir-i Khusraw who had visited Injigan with his disciples. Phatak's practices and ritualistic expressions reflect deeper cultural layers of Central Asia as well as indigenous seasonal symbolism. Study suggests that Phatak signifies a dynamic fusion of Central Asian traditions and Islamic reformative ideals, highlighting how festivals play significant role in preserving cultural memories while sustaining social and moral order within a particular community.*

Keywords: Aminako Bashad, Bash, Chilla Kashi, Ishperi, Khowar, Khalifa, Luqma, Mubarako Bashad, Nasir-i Khusraw, Nowruz, Phatak, Pirniki, Phathakin, Oazi, Sadat, Samun.

Introduction

The preservation and protection of cultural heritage serve as the foundation for communal identity, connecting as bridge between a community's historical and cultural roots and its contemporary social dynamics. Across the mountainous regions of Central Asia particularly Northern areas of Pakistan, local cultural festivals function not merely as events of celebration, but as dynamic sources of social order, ethical values, and historical memories. These diverse traditions provide a sense of endurance that maintain the communal essence against the pressures of globalization and contemporary cultural homogenization. The significance of this connection between cultural preservation and communal identity is poignantly captured by the National Poet of Pakistan Dr. Allama Muhammad Iqbal in his famous book Rumūz-e-Bekhudi.

زنده قوم از ارتباط جان و تن

زنده قوم از حفظ ناموس کهن

Translation: "As life of a human is sustained through the combination of physical body and abstract soul, similarly the life of a nation (community) depends upon the

preservation and protection of its cultural heritage and valuable traditions”.

One of the most energetic and comprehensive means of preserving cultural heritage and historical memories is the celebration of diverse festivals. Through such activities and practices, a nation not only protect its valuable traditions and cultural values but also derives ethical, social and collective benefits. The history of these festivals is closely entwined with the creation of human being and origin of the society, and their diverse ways of celebration has taken various forms with the passage of time and space. Festival celebrations is a constant process that continues as long as human societies and concept of community exist, highlighting the inevitable relationship between human existence and rituals celebration.

Recognizing the importance of historical cultural festivals, religious and social reformers have often utilized them as vehicle of ethical revival and social transformation. In many accounts, these reformers have introduced new rituals and festivals to inspire people ethical awareness and promote collective social development. Therefore, all festivals carry their own historic and cultural foundations and social connotations, which directly or indirectly contribute to various aspects of human moral and social development.

In the similar context, the people of Injigan annually celebrate a unique cultural cum religious festival known as ‘Phatak’, which symbolizes rich ethical, cultural social dimensions. Indigenous traditions attribute the origin of this beautiful festival to the 11th century prominent Ismaili scholar and philosopher Hakeem Nasir-i Khusraw (1004-1088).

Historical background

In Khowar (Chitrali language), the term “Phatak” literally means “white sign.” With regard to the historical context of this festival, it signifies the ritual of sprinkling wheat flour on the five wooden pillars inside the traditional Central Asian houses in the early morning of the festival, is called “Phatak.” This cultural festival itself derives its name from this unique ritual of sprinkling wheat flour on the five pillars which is considered the essential symbolic expression of the celebration. The festival is celebrated in Injigan, Chitral every year from January 31 to February 1, with enthusiasm and communal participation. Historically, this festival was celebrated in several parts of Lotkuh (Lower Chitral), such as Arkari, Karimabad, and Shoghor, as well as in some areas of Upper Chitral. However, with the passage of time, the practice was discontinued for unknown reasons. (Shireen K. personal communication, Dec 12, 2025). One of the competent scholars of history, Mr. Arshad Irfan, explains: “Phatak refers to the traditional act of welcoming things by sprinkling flour. The festival came to be known as Phatak because it celebrates the arrival of spring. He also explains that starting on February 1, young markhor kids begin to avoid direct sunlight because the sun becomes warmer. (Irfan. A, personal communication, Dec 15, 2025).

According to local tradition, the Phatak festival is observed primarily in the region

between Mogh and Shahsalim, because it is generally believed that Hakeem Nasir Khusraw did not proceed beyond the village of Mogh in Garam Chashma toward Chitral. Although research on the origin and evolution of this festival remains limited, most writers, including the Sadat families of Injigan, who have been playing a central role in organizing the festival, associate it with the 11th-century prominent Ismaili scholar Nasir-i Khusraw. According to local tradition, the festival was first observed when Hakeem Nasir-i Khusraw completed his forty-day meditation (Chilla Kashi) in a cave near the Ziyarat, Injigan. The community has also constructed an Astana (shrine) in the area where Nasir-i Khusraw reportedly stayed for several days. Multiple sources confirm Nasir-i Khusraw's visit to Injigan, Chitral. For instance, Faizi (1996) notes: "Naser-e-Khusrow visited Chitral through the Munjan Valley. He is said to have spent forty days in a hut at Garm Chashma, which is now known as the Ziyarat (shrine) of Naser-e-Khusrow"(p.78). Professor Bhamiyani (2000) similarly reports: "Naser-e-Khusraw visited Garm Chashma with his four companions. He meditated in a cave for forty days" (p. 58). According to Bhamiyani, one of his companions was Syed Malik Jahan Shah, generally known as Umar Yumgi, to whom the Sadat of Injigan trace their genealogy. A Tajik scholar, Shaftalov Ghulamadov, critically analyzes sources regarding Nasir-i Khusraw's visits to the region in his Ph.D. thesis, noting that...

He (Danial Baben) points out that, in addition to an account of Nasir Khusraw's life and mission to Badakhshan, this text (Sayahat Nama'i Nasir) offers of his travel to neighboring region such as Tibbet, which seems to be mis-reading as the Siyahat nama'i Nasir offers no such account, although it certainly narrates stories about the travels to other regions of Badakhshan (Kuhistan), including Chitral (Chitrar), the regions of Upper Oxus valley, and those on the right side of the Punj river mentioned by Ivanow. (p.248)

By referring to a famous book, Bahr-ul Akhbar, Siyahat-i Nasir, he further discusses the divisions of the regions of Badakhshan among the students of Nasir-i Khusraw. He writes,

Nasir-i Khusraw then divides the places (takavah) under the dawa between Syed Suhrab and Malik Jahan Shah (Umar Yumgi). Places such as Sangtigh (probably Sanglich), Zibak, Ishkasum, Vakhan, Shughnan, Rushan, and Darvaz are placed under Syed Suhrab's control. Other places, including Shah Salim, Chitrar, Khash (In Yumgan Valley), Ispanj, and other areas, are assigned to Malik Jahan Shah. (p.257)

In addition, several other prominent writers, including Mirza Muhammad Ghufan (1962), Dr. Naik Alam Rashid (2004), Abdullah Jan (2008), and Muhammad Irfan (2025), also acknowledge that Nasir-i Khusraw and his disciples traveled to this region. Moreover, the presence of the descendants of Umar Yumgi in Injigan further corroborates the connection of this festival with Nasir-i Khusraw and his companions.

The Sadat of Injigan, locally referred as Darwesh, have traditionally served as Khalifas and Qazis, bearing the responsibility for conducting a range of Jamati rituals, like

festivals, marriage ceremonies, funeral rites, and other religious and cultural practices. They have also preserved manuscripts, banners, Chiragh Dan, and traditional Chugha (long coat), which they associate with Nasir-i Khusraw, alongside oral traditions recounting the visits of Nasir-i Khusraw and his disciples to Chitral. Although the festival of Phatak sustains its visible connections with Nasir Khusraw and Ismaili theological doctrines, its cultural importance is particularly evident in its pluralistic history of diverse communal participation that transcends all religious affiliations.

Nature of Celebration

Historically the Darvesh family of Injigan and the notables of the area bear broad responsibility for the organization and management of the festival, which is one of the major reasons it has maintained its original shape. A committee consisting Qazis and Khalifas of the Darvesh family invite a meeting of social workers and volunteers approximately a week before the festival to discuss the plan for organizing the festival. The committee create small groups, consisting of two or three members, who are assigned to visit different villages to convey guidelines related to the celebration of the festival and also to recite few verses from Persian prayers along with best wishes. Before their assignments, these particular groups of volunteers undergo a brief training program so that they can learn the procedures for celebrating the festival. For instance, the exact timing of the ritual of sprinkling Phatak on the pillars can vary from year to year, and other dimension of the festival also require updated guidelines time to time. After proper training, these groups depart for their respective locations two or three days before the festival. These volunteers are locally known as Phathakin and they are warmly welcomed by people, who also present them with various gifts as tokens of respect and appreciation. (Nadir. S, personal communication, Dec. 17, 2025).

The day earlier Phatak is called ‘Samun’, which means preparation. On this day, households clean their traditional houses and do not permit anyone from outside to enter until the following day. The ceilings of the traditional houses are often blackened by soot from wood fires, making this a dedicated day to remove dust from walls and ceilings. On the morning of Phatak, an elder visits each house and recites Persian verses as part of a prayer, entering with the phrase Mubārakō Bāshad (Congratulations), to which the insiders respond Āmīnākō Bāshad (May it be accepted). Early in the morning, usually around five o’clock, the head of the family applies Phatak to the five main pillars of the house, symbolizing the family’s prosperity and happiness. It is customary that this particular ritual is performed while facing the Qibla (Ka’bah). The contrast of white flour against the darkened walls and ceilings allows for decorative patterns, which households create on both walls and ceilings. Following this rite, groups of villagers visit each house. Upon entering, the head of the household applies Phatak to the right shoulder of each member of the visiting group, while the exchange of wishes Mubārakō Bāshad and Āmīnākō Bāshad are repeated.

Although a variety of dishes are prepared during the festival, most are prepared from

milk. A unique sweet dish Shoshpalaki, is cooked on this occasion and presented to the guests. Its preparation involves a lengthy process, likely spanning twenty-five days, which begins about a month before the festival. The wheat undergoes a prolonged process to develop its sweet taste; once dried, it is ground and then cooked. On the day of the festival, Shoshpalaki is cooked in every household across the valley. Before serving Shoshpalaki, Ishperi (cheese) is presented which is considered a good sign. Additionally, wheat bread known as Pirniki is prepared in every house for the shrine of Nasir-i Khusraw. The head of each family delivers these offerings, along with other Nazranas (offerings) to the Ziyarat, where members of the Sadat families receive them, offer prayers, and return a small portion of a specially prepared traditional dish, usually Shanek, which is considered sacred and termed as Luqma (Younus. S, personal communication, Dec, 15, 2025).

Like other celebrations and festivals, people make new clothes for the event, and in many places traditional musical programs are also organized. Various traditional games, such as hockey, Rasa Kashi (tug of war), football etc. and, are also played. Girls also gather in particular areas to swing and sing. On this day, families send special bread, dishes, and gifts to the homes of their married daughters and sisters, a practice known as Bash. Sometimes, entire families visit their married daughters or sisters in person on this occasion. Overall, the festival serves a significant social function, fostering communal bonds and bringing people together.

Social and Moral Aspects of Phatak

No festival in the world is without objectives and lessons behind its visible form. Every festival has been formed in such a way where it deals directly or indirectly with any aspect of human society, whether it is related to the ethics or social aspects of life. Because of the social and ethical underpinnings of these festivals, they acquire very much cultural importance in any society. Similarly, 'Phatak' is a festival that deals with many ethical and social aspects of the indigenous society. Some of the major social and reconciliatory aspects of 'Phatak' will be discussed as follows.

1. The central component of this festival consists of activities related to cleaning and maintenance. Approximately one week before Phatak, a collective cleaning process begins. During this period, not only houses are cleaned and repaired, but streets and pathways are also cleaned and maintained by the community. It seems that this festival is proposed for a systematic way of cleaning the traditional houses, which particularly become black and dusty over time due to huge soot from firewood inside the houses. This festival emphasizes on the purity and cleanliness which is one of the basic ethical responsibilities in Islamic teachings.
2. Phatak also encourages social and communal unity within the local people. Due to the extreme weather conditions in winter, social interaction opportunities become very limited, and it provides a meaningful opportunity for people of Injigan to meet each other and share their happiness at the Ziyarat of Hakeem Nasir-i Khusraw. This opportunity

boosts social awareness and mutual respect among community members of the area. Moreover, visiting relatives during this occasion reflects a bond of love, affection, and care, which strengthens the familial and communal connections.

3. Another significant aspect of the festival is its reconciliatory dimension, that strengthens communal and familial relationships. This festival provides a wonderful opportunity for reconciliation among estranged and separated families. In the beginning of the festival, elders and notables of the area actively involved in mediating between disputing parties, appreciating them to set aside their grudges and renew their social and familial connections. Through these worth practices, the festival also serves as a powerful mechanism for social harmony, bringing families and individuals closer to each other.

Conclusion

In conclusion, cultural values and principals are fundamentally abstract in nature and convert into visibility through their incorporation with cultural, social and traditional frameworks such as rituals, rites and diverse festivals. In that context, Phatak signifies far more than a simple cultural or seasonal celebration rather represents a very deeply rooted Central Asian connections that integrates ethical dimensions, historical memories, spiritual symbolism, and social solidarity. Its direct association with the eminent scholar Hakim Nasir-i Khusraw provides it with a meaningful cultural, intellectual and religious significance. Through its key aspect such as concept of purification, communal harmony, and arbitration, Phatak strengthens fundamental ethical values like unity, cleanliness, and social cohesion. Moreover, Phatak serves as a living source of collective identity, preserving the valuable cultural heritage of the region while fostering intergenerational continuity. Eventually, it illustrates how cultural festivals can function as powerful tool to maintain both cultural resilience and social order in far-flung mountain communities like Chitral. It is also significant to recognize and encourage such festivals, as they appreciate social cohesion and values that are crucial to maintain the meaningful social fabric of society. The government and civil society organizations should actively support such festivals to ensure their continuity.

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